

Studies on 2-Salicylhydrazonobenzothiazole Metal Chelates as Potent Antifungal and Antibacterial Drugs

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The benzothiazoles¹, thiosemicarbazones and thiazolyl hydrazones² and azo compounds³ are known to possess various biological activities. It has been observed that some drugs increase the activity when administered as metal complex, more so their metal chelates⁴.

We report here the synthesis of the benzothiazole ligand and its metal complexes with bivalent Cu, Co, Ni, Cd, Fe and Zn. Their antibacterial and antifungal activities have been evaluated.

Results and Discussion

The metal-ligand ratio in all the complexes (Table 1) was found to be 1 : 2.

IR spectra of all the complexes revealed bands at 3 290–3 690 (OH phenolic), 1 680 (CH=N), 1 610–1 510 (aromatic ring), 3 300–3 350 (NH–N=), 2 040–1 920 (N=C=S) and 850 cm⁻¹ (2 adjacent aromatic C–H). The disappearance of H-bonded OH in the ligand and its reappearance in the metal chelates are suggestive of –O–M–N bond formation (where M is metal atom). The ligand

band of medium intensity around 1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=N) shifted to lower value with weak intensity in the spectra of chelates. It is due to M←N bond formation. The bands at 1 610–1 510 cm⁻¹ are due to aromatic rings. The ligand bands at 2 040–1 920 cm⁻¹ (–N=C–S) remained unchanged, suggesting that metal complex formation does not take place around the –N=C–S group.

Antibacterial and antifungal activities : The antifungal activity was screened against *A. niger* and *P. digitatum* using a solution of the compound in 5% DMF in acetone by cup-plate agar diffusion technique. All the fungal cultures were maintained on Sabourauds agar slant⁶. Most of the compounds showed 70% inhibition at a concentration of 500 ppm; compounds 3 and 4 showed more than 70% inhibition at a lower concentration (250 ppm).

Antibacterial activity was determined following the cup-plate agar diffusion technique⁷, against *S. aureus* and *Micrococcus leutius*. A 1% (w/v) solution of each compound in a mixture of 5% DMF and acetone was used. After incubation for 24 h at 37° the zone of inhibition was measured and result compared with the control (Table 1).

Compound 5 showed little activity towards *S. aureus* and *M. leuteus* and no activity against *P. digitatum*, *A. niger*, and 3 showed good activity against all the microorganisms. The results

TABLE 1—ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY DATA OF THE COMPLEX*

Compd. no.	Compd.	Colour	<i>M. leuitius</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>P. digitatum</i>
1	Fe[SHBT] ₂	Brown	20.8	18.9	18.0	16.7
2	Ni[SHBT] ₂	Almond	21.2	21.7	24.1	22.7
3	Cu[SHBT] ₂	Brown	23.5	22.4	27.0	25.4
4	Zn[SHBT] ₂	Yellow	22.3	21.3	23.2	24.1
5	Pb[SHBT] ₂	Yellow	18.5	16.2	—	—
	2-Salicyl hydrazono- benzothiazole		10.6	10.9	11.7	10.4

*All compounds gave satisfactory N, S and metal analyses; m.p. 300°.

reveal that antibacterial and antifungal activities are enhanced on complexation of 2-salicylhydrazonobenzothiazole with the metals.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The metal-ligand ratio was determined by conductometric titration and Job's method of continuous variations. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer. Metals were estimated by standard methods⁵, sulphur by Messenger's method and C, H, N by a micro-analyser.

A mixture of equimolecular quantities of salicylaldehyde and 2-hydrazonobenzothiazole was heated on a water-bath for 30–35 min and then cooled. The resulting crystals of 2-salicylhydrazonobenzothiazole were washed well with warm water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

Preparation of complexes : Aqueous solution of salts of Cu^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Fe^{II} or Ni^{II} was added to the ligand (2-salicylhydrazonobenzothiazole) dropwise at 50–60°. Its pH was maintained at 8–9 by using 0.1 M H₃BO₃ (8.5–21.3 ml). The resulting solid chelates were washed with hot water, crystallised from 50% acetic acid and dried (110–120°).

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